

attacked more heavily than first-crop fields. Rice fields under shifting cultivation on hill slopes were not infested.

A study was made in 1973 kharif to determine the extent of infestation and the "hot spots" in Imphal, where most rice cultivation is confined.

The pest is well established in the major rice belt of Manipur, extending south to the Bishenpur block and north to Kangpokpi. Observations during the past 4 to 5 years confirm that the pest is building up in the state, necessitating regular chemical control as that for yellow stem borer and gall midge.

Further buildup of the pest cannot be ruled out, considering the changed agricultural strategy in Manipur brought about by the introduction of more high-yielding varieties, the extension of areas under such varieties, heavier fertilizer applications, and increased cropping intensity. Along with the rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis*, leaf butterfly is fast emerging as a pest at early growth stages of the second paddy crop — the bulk of rice production in the state. ■

Chemical control of the brown planthopper

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A study to determine suitable pesticides for control of the brown planthopper (BPH) was conducted in our field in kharif 1978.

The trial was laid out in a randomized block design, replicated four times. The insecticides fenitrothion, monocrotophos, ethion, and quinalphos at 0.05%

Brown planthopper incidence and rice yields on plots treated with various chemicals. Mangalore, India.

Treatment ^a	BPH (mean no./ 5 hills)	Mean yield (kg/plot)
Fenitrothion	27.2	2.0
Monocrotophos	15.2	2.3
Ethion	8.0	3.0
Quinalphos	35.2	1.8
Control	67.5	0.9
CD at 0.5%	12.57	0.22

^aAll treatments applied at 0.05%.

concentration were compared with an untreated control. They were sprayed at crop growth stages from the nursery to the hard dough stage. The BPH on five randomly selected hills per replication were counted before and periodically after each spraying.

All the insecticidal sprays significantly reduced BPH infestation and increased yields over that of the control (see table). Treatments with ethion were most effective, followed by those with monocrotophos and fenitrothion. ■

Hopperburn by the orange-headed leafhopper in Bangladesh

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In Bangladesh, hopperburn caused by the brown planthopper, whitebacked planthopper, and green leafhopper was previously reported. This is the first report on hopperburn caused by the orange-headed leafhopper (OHLH) *Thaia oryzivora* Ghauri.

Ghauri (1962) described the new genus *Thaia* and the new species *Thaia oryzivora* on paddy in Thailand. Smaller than *Nephotettix* spp., OHLH can be easily identified by its orange-colored head and subhyaline fore wings. This leafhopper was first recorded in Bangladesh — on wheat in 1964 and on rice in 1968 — by H. Z. Alam. Ahmed and Samad (1972) regarded the insect as a pest of economic importance in Bangladesh. It usually feeds on the undersurface of leaves, causing necrotic lesions around feeding sites. The badly affected leaves show white scars or irregular lines on the upper surfaces. Adults and nymphs produce similar damage. Alam and Alam (1977) reported that the insect breeds actively in October and November and again in February and March, producing high populations during those periods.

Hopperburn occurred the last week of March in areas with controlled irrigation in the Dacca area. There was standing water in the fields and rice growth was luxuriant. Hopperburn occurred from flowering to the hard dough stage in IR8, especially that planted in November or

early December. It did not occur on BR3, BR6, and Pajam II. Although OHLH caused negligible hopperburn, it is a potential pest of rice in Bangladesh. ■

Chironomid fauna of Korea and their role in the rice agroecosystem

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Chironomids are the most numerous insects in the rice paddy ecosystem in Korea. However, the significance of chironomid fauna in the ecosystem is not known.

In the summer 1975, Yasumatsu and Chang collected chironomids in the rice paddies of Suweon, Korea. Hashimoto identified the specimens as follows:

1. *Smittia* sp.
2. *Mesosmittia* (?) sp.
3. *Chironomus nipponensis* Tokunaga
4. *Chironomus plumosus* Linnaeus
5. *Syncricotopus rufiventris* (Meigen)
6. *Cricotopus trifasciatus* Panzer
7. *Harnischia* sp.
8. *Orthocladus suspensus* Tokunaga
9. *Eukiefeeriella* sp.

The only chironomid species previously reported from Korea is *Chironomus oryzae* Matzumura. But it was not identified by a specialist. We believe that the species identified as *Chironomus oryzae* is *C. plumosus*. More material is still under taxonomic study by Hashimoto, and more species will later be added to the list.

Most species of chironomids breed in dead organic matter and the adults emerge in large numbers. Predators, such as spiders and damselflies, feed on them and also on pests that breed on the rice plant (see figure).

Chironomids are significant to the agrosystem. Throughout the vast rice areas of Asia they serve as an alternative food of predators and thus help conserve predators when rice pests are scarce. Chironomids are often more abundant and easily captured than rice pests.

Relationship of predator to chironomids and rice pests in the rice ecosystem.

Because predators tend to capture them rather than the other insects, the beneficial effects of predators is reduced. In some fields, spiders have no effect on the pest population when the chironomid population is high.

Any field research on rice pests and predators that ignores chironomids is unrealistic and may give unreliable information on the development of integrated rice pest control. With Thai entomologists, Yasumatsu and Hashimoto are making an extensive survey of the chironomid fauna in the rice paddies of Thailand. ■

Occurrence of *Sogatodes oryricola* (Muir) in upland rice in Goiás, Brasil

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During 1977–78 a preliminary survey of insect pests of upland rice in the experimental fields of the National Rice

and Beans Research Center in Goiania revealed diverse species of leafhoppers and planthoppers in the cultivar IAC47. The insect that occurred most frequently was *Sogatodes oryricola* (Fulgoroidea – Delphacidae) (see table). This insect, a vector of the virus disease hoja blanca, is an important rice pest in Latin American countries. It was first reported in Brazil at Resende, Rio de Janeiro, as *Sogatodes brazilensis*. In 1965, R. G. Fennah considered it as a synonym of *S. oryricola*. The host species or the latter has, however, not been reported. Thus, this note is the first report of *S. oryricola* as a rice pest in Brazil. Compared with the various leafhoppers and planthoppers counted on the cultivar IAC47,

Percentage incidence of *Sogatodes oryricola* in a leafhopper and planthopper population established on the cultivar IAC47, Brazil, 1977–78.

Collection time (days after sowing)	<i>S. oryricola</i> (%)		
	Adults	Nymphs	Total
45	17	2	19
58	18	60	78
80	25	68	93
104	9	90	99
130	48	49	97

S. oryricola had a high population.

Hoja blanca disease has not yet been reported in Brazil, but because a vector exists, appropriate measures should be considered to prevent the introduction and spread of a potential cause of large crop losses. ■

Tetrastichus sp. (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae), a new parasitoid-predator of the brown planthopper

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During investigations on mymarid egg parasitoids, larvae of *Tetrastichus* sp. were often found preying on eggs of brown and whitebacked planthoppers at IRRI. The hymenopteran had never been known to attack the eggs of rice hoppers, but further investigations revealed its remarkable parasitic and predatory habits.

Adults are about 1.2 mm long, yellow with brown spots, and have 4-segmented tarsi and greatly enlarged antennal scapes (see figure). They parasitize brown planthopper eggs inside which the first-instar larva develops by feeding on the egg contents. Parasitized host eggs are indistinguishable from those parasitized by mymarids — both turn yellow. Unlike mymarids, which complete their entire life cycle in one host egg, *Tetrastichus* larvae that have consumed the host egg contents emerge and behave like predators by feeding on several additional host eggs before pupating in the leaf sheath tissue. Young larvae are colorless with a yellow-pigmented alimentary canal and sharp mandibles. As they feed, their gut turns reddish and increases greatly in size. The pupa is naked, white with

bright red eyes and ocelli, and has a yellow mass in the middle of the abdomen (see figure). Adults emerge after a pupal period of 4 days.

The field population of this parasitoid-predator does not appear high compared with that of the mymarid and trichogrammatid parasitoids. The larvae may still contribute to significant pest mortality because each normally destroys several host eggs before pupating. ■

Tetrastichus sp.: 1) full-grown larva, 2) pupa, 3) adult (female).